

THE ISSUE OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF A WITNESS INVOLVED IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

A.S.Pulatov

Doctor of Law, Associate Professor

Independent researcher at the Academy of Justice.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17937067>

Annotation: This article analyzes the issue of ensuring the safety of a witness involved in criminal proceedings. Also, the necessity of taking measures to ensure the safety of the witness by the investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, and court was studied if there is sufficient information to say that there is a threat to the life, health, and property of the witness. In addition, national and foreign experience in the field of work was studied, and proposals and recommendations for the relevant legislation were made.

Keywords: criminal procedure, witness, rights and obligations, interrogation, information, pseudonym, security, evidence, testimony, social protection, responsibility.

In the Criminal Procedure Code of our country, the relationship arising in the matter of ensuring the safety of a witness involved in criminal proceedings can be seen mainly in the norms of two articles. For example, Article 270, known as "Ensuring the Security of Participants in Criminal Proceedings," states that if there is sufficient information to believe that the life, health, or property of a witness (as well as other participants in criminal proceedings) is threatened, the investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, or court must take measures to ensure the witness's safety.

Article 380 of the Criminal Procedure Code also establishes the procedural order for ensuring the safety of individual persons involved in criminal proceedings. According to the content of the article, "in order to ensure the safety of victims, witnesses, attesting witnesses, and other participants in the proceedings, their pseudonyms may be indicated in the list of persons to be summoned to the court session. Information about persons in need of security is submitted to the court with a seal along with the introductory parts of the protocols of investigative actions conducted with their participation. Only the prosecutor approving the indictment and the judge considering the case can familiarize themselves with them.

In national legislation, one can see some shortcomings related to the procedural basis for ensuring the safety of a witness. These shortcomings are not only of an organizational and legal nature, but also of a functional nature. In particular, these are: a) the safety rules apply only to the witness (other

participants whose safety is ensured), their relatives are excluded from these measures; b) the scope of procedural and legal measures to ensure the safety of the witness (as well as other participants whose safety is ensured) is not clearly defined; c) the procedures for implementing procedural and legal measures to ensure the safety of a witness do not have a clear form and content (for example, who, in what order, and on the basis of which procedural act is authorized to ensure the safety of a witness); d) the grounds for protecting the rights and legitimate interests of the accused (suspect, defendant) are not provided for when implementing procedural and legal measures to ensure the safety of a witness.

In the Criminal Procedure Code of the country, there are no norms regulating the participation of a person under a pseudonym when there is a need to ensure the safety of the person who reported the crime, on the basis of which the act of initiating a criminal case was adopted as a result of the pre-investigation check.

In accordance with parts one and two of Article 324 of the Criminal Procedure Code, "statements of persons about a crime may be written or oral. The written application must be signed by the applicant.

The oral application is recorded in the minutes. The record must contain information about the applicant, their place of residence and work, as well as personal documents...."

However, these procedural rules cannot be applied to a person who has expressed a desire to participate under a pseudonym, whose information, explanations, and testimony are significant for conducting a preliminary investigation or inquiry, as well as for the purposes of ensuring the safety of this person.

Some procedural scholars emphasize that, on the contrary, in order to ensure the safety of the person who reported the crime, it is not permissible to conceal information relating to their personality, as well as to use a "pen name" instead of the information of the person who reported the crime in the decision to initiate a criminal case. It is appropriate to protect the safety of the reporting person at the next stage of criminal proceedings - the preliminary investigation¹.

Proponents of this view base their opinion on three aspects: firstly, at this stage, the issue of initiating or denying a criminal case is mainly resolved, therefore the legal status of the person who reported the crime is also not clear; secondly, referring to a pseudonym, not a real person, in the decision to initiate a criminal case may cause many objections and distrust on the part of the defense;

¹ Масалан қаралсин: Сулейменова Г. Ж. Проблемы участия в уголовном процессе свидетелей под псевдонимом. Журнал Online.zakon.kz. 2017. –С.71-74. https://Document/?doc_id=31424328 #pos=6; -116.

thirdly, it can cause serious difficulties in the implementation of the task of proof, which is the responsibility of the competent persons conducting the criminal case.

The problems associated with a witness participating under a pseudonym mainly consist of these two opposing approaches. Which viewpoint is valid on this issue, and which one is not sufficiently justified? In the search for an answer to the question, it is necessary to clarify several important premises related to the issue. These include: a) reporting a crime of a high degree of social danger (a grave or especially grave crime); b) the characteristics of the evidence to be established during the pre-investigation check conducted on the basis of the person's report on the crime, or the evidence established as a result of it (for example, the establishment of evidence for initiating a criminal case); c) the nature of the decision that can be made or expected as a result of the pre-investigation check (the sufficiency of the evidence and information to be established in the initial period of the investigation or as a result of it for initiating a criminal case); d) the nature of the relationship between the person who committed the offense (close relative, acquaintance, for example, a neighbor, a colleague, a person who suddenly became a witness to the crime, etc.) in the information of the reporting person (applicant); e) the nature of the procedural status he occupies in a criminal case that is clearly initiated on the basis of the person's report on the crime (for example: witness, victim, civil claimant, participant in the crime); f) the degree of

Thus, the above-mentioned characteristics are considered important grounds for deciding whether to apply measures to ensure the safety of the person who reported the crime immediately or when there is no possibility of delay.

However, to ensure the functioning of these foundations, it is advisable to solve another problem. The issue under consideration is related to what procedural rule or security mechanism should be activated by the person who reported it (the applicant), if there is a need to keep their personal data confidential. If, when it is necessary to ensure the safety of a witness or other participants in criminal proceedings, the person conducting the pre-investigation check must adopt a certain procedural act, for example, a decision, then, unlike the decision to initiate or refuse to initiate a criminal case, it is necessary to grant the procedural subject conducting the pre-investigation check the authority to make a decision on taking measures to ensure the safety of the person.

Today, one can observe a significant increase in actions that prevent a witness from giving accurate and truthful testimony. Various external pressures and pressure on a witness are aimed at changing the content and essence of the

information they possess that is significant for resolving a criminal case. The methods of such external influence are also changing, including pressure and pressure on close relatives of the witness or with their participation.

Considering these circumstances, the legislative bodies of various countries have developed procedural norms regulating the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of participants in criminal proceedings, in particular, the witness, as an object of protection. For example, in accordance with Article 68 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Georgia, the following special measures for the protection of a witness (and other participants) may be applied: a) removal of entries and records from all public registers that allow for the identification and determination of the witness's identity, including - name, patronymic, surname, address, place of work, profession, or other information; b) ensuring the confidentiality of documents that allow for the identification and determination of the witness's procedural documents, as well as the information specified in paragraph "a" of this article; c) providing a pseudonym; d) applying security measures; e) changing appearance; f) changing permanent or temporary residence.

The norms of the criminal procedure law of the Russian Federation are of interest in this matter. Unlike most Commonwealth countries, the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation reflects measures ensuring the safety of a witness (other participants) in several norms. These are: a) failure to indicate in the interrogation record information relating to the identity of the witness and close relatives, as well as recording information under a pseudonym (Clause 9 of Article 166 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); b) monitoring and recording telephone and other conversations conducted by the witness and close relatives (Clause 2 of Article 186 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); c) conducting an identification investigative action that restricts direct contact between the identifier and the person being identified (Clause 8 of Article 193 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation); d) conducting an interrogation of a witness in conditions that restrict the possibility of direct observation, as well as ensuring the confidentiality of personal data relating to the witness (Clause 5 of Article 278 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation)².

Security measures provided for by Russian legislation have more procedural content than security measures established by Georgian legislation. The most

² Уголовно-процессуальный кодекс Российской Федерации. Статьи 167, 280. от 18 декабря 2001 г. N 174-ФЗ.

important requirement for ensuring witness safety in this law is, firstly, to ensure the confidentiality of information about the witness (other participants); secondly, to limit the direct confrontation between the witness and the accused (suspect, defendant).

An important aspect of this issue is the confidentiality of information about the witness, as well as the modification of official information identifying his identity, and the maintenance of procedural documents related to the witness under a pseudonym.

Maintaining the confidentiality of information about the identity of witnesses and creating procedural conditions that restrict their direct face-to-face meetings with the suspect, accused, defendant is one of the important measures of procedural and legal security of witnesses in connection with the performance of their duties in the course of criminal proceedings in almost all CIS countries.

It should be noted that in the procedural norms of other countries related to this issue, one can find two phrases and concepts related to ensuring the safety of witnesses. In particular, in the CIS member states, when ensuring the safety of a witness, his personal data is kept secret under a pseudonym. In many Western countries that apply security measures of the same nature, such persons have the status of confidential witnesses.

Of course, from the point of view of phraseology, these terms are united by a single general concept. That is, in order to protect a person from various external influences that threaten the performance of his duty in the process of justice - the transfer of information known to him on the circumstances of the criminal case, as well as the application of such security measures as the restriction of his face-to-face meetings (contact) with other interested persons participating in the case in procedural actions with the participation of this person.

Thus, in the "Recommendations on the Practice of Witness Protection in Organized Crime Proceedings" of the UN Committee on Drugs and Crime on the Safety of Witnesses, it is recognized that various attacks and harassment against witnesses by organized criminal groups are being committed in the international arena, and it is emphasized that the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of witnesses from any encroachments is a pressing problem in the field of judicial proceedings today³.

An important place in the "Recommendations" is given to an anonymous witness, that is, a witness who participates secretly. According to this document,

³ Рекомендуемые виды практики в области защиты свидетелей при производстве по уголовным делам, касающимся организованной преступности. Организация объединенных наций, Нью-Йорк, 2008 год

an anonymous (classified) witness is the confidentiality of the witness's personal data in whole or in part. The "Recommendations" also emphasize that the confidentiality of the personal data of a witness protected from harm to their interests is an effective procedural method of witness protection. Because an important issue here is the concealment of the identity of the witness giving testimony about information relevant to the case, and the circumstances of the testimony can be confirmed by other evidence available in the case⁴.

According to the "Recommendations," the criminal procedure legislation of countries that provide for a participant with the status of an anonymous (classified) witness establishes the following procedure for discussing their testimony: a) maintaining a separate record of the witness's personal data from the minutes of the court hearing and keeping them out of the public domain; b) prosecuting and punishing, within the framework of the law, actions aimed at exposing the identity of a classified witness⁵.

The following circumstances serve as the basis for the court's decision to ensure the safety of a witness using procedural means: 1) the nature of the crime (members of an organized criminal group, crimes against sexual freedom, crimes committed within the framework of family and domestic relations, etc.); 2) classification characteristics of witnesses (victims) (child, victim of sexual assault, member of a criminal group that made a transaction, etc.); 3) the degree of relationship between the accused and the witness (relative, a person dependent on the accused, a member of a criminal group led by the accused, etc.); 4) the degree of violence and harassment that can be committed against a witness; 5) the significance for the case of the information contained in the witness's testimony⁶.

The "Guidelines on Criminal Procedure," prepared by the OSCE General Secretariat for member states and countries with relations based on mutual partnership under the idea of a European "common home," recognizes that various attacks and harassment against witnesses are being committed in the international arena, and emphasizes that protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of witnesses from any encroachments is a pressing issue in the field of legal proceedings today⁷.

⁴ Рекомендуемые виды практики в области защиты свидетелей при производстве по уголовным делам, касающимся организованной преступности. Организация объединенных наций, Нью-Йорк, 2008 год. –С.31.

⁵ Қайд этилган манбанинг 32-бети.

⁶ Ўша манбанинг 33-бети.

⁷ Бюллетень Европейского Суда по правам человека. Российское издание. М., 2003. N 1. С. 34.

The document states that confidentiality is one of the effective ways to protect the rights and interests of witnesses. In particular, in connection with the implementation in the judicial practice of the European Court of Human Rights of Article 6 (i.e., the right to a fair trial) and in accordance with the provisions of the Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Freedom⁸ of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the participation of a confidential witness is permitted, procedural conditions for its implementation are established, and 46 countries have acceded to this Convention⁹.

Foreign scientists distinguish two types of methods that effectively ensure the safety of witnesses - the state of personal confidentiality. In particular, according to the German scientist, the secrecy that is ensured in relation to witnesses in the presence of a certain danger is: 1) partial or limited secrecy; 2) absolute or complete confidentiality¹⁰ types are available.

The concept of partial or limited confidentiality refers to the fact that a witness is allowed to perform only certain procedural obligations. Accordingly, the witness must answer the defense's questions during the trial. In this case, the witness has the right not to answer the question about the disclosure of their last name, first name, profession, place of work, and other personal data¹¹.

According to many scientists and law enforcement officers, such a means of witness protection, in practice, allows for the involvement in criminal proceedings of persons with a confidential status involved in operational-search activities, whose names remain confidential due to the risk of disclosure¹². Such witnesses (often operational-search personnel, employees of state security agencies, etc.) give testimony in court proceedings mainly under pseudonyms¹³.

⁸ United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 213, No. 2889

⁹ *Kostovski v. The Netherlands*, Judgement of 20 November 1989, Application No. 11451/85, Series A, No. 166; *Windisch v. Austria*, Judgement of 27 September 1990, Application No. 12489/86, Series A, No. 186; *Lydi v. Switzerland*, Judgement of 15 June 1992, Application No. 12433/86, Series A, No. 238; and *Doorson v. The Netherlands*, Judgement of 26 March 1996, Application No. 20524/92, Reports 1996-II).

¹⁰ *Huber B.* Development of the Criminal Law: Review// European Journal of Crime, Criminal Law and Criminal Justice 1993.

¹¹ *Ashworth A.* The Criminal Process : An Evaluative Study. Oxford, 1994

¹² Масалан каранг: *Епихин А. Ю., Мишин А. В.* Допрос потерпевшего, свидетеля под псевдонимом в досудебном и судебном производствах (уголовно-процессуальные и криминалистические аспекты). Проведение. Том 29, №4, 2019. –С.480-486; *Каранетьян С.А., Олефиренко С.П.* Защита участников уголовного судопроизводства: использование псевдонимов в уголовно-процессуальных законодательствах зарубежных государств постсоветского периода //Международный студенческий научный вестник. №4 (часть 4), 2015. –С.642-644.

¹³ *Burnham W.* Introduction to the Law and Legal System of the United States. West Publishing, 1994. *Braithwaite J., Mugford S.* Conditions of Successful Reintegration Ceremonies: Dealing with Juvenile Offenders// British Journal of Criminology. 1994. № 34.

References used:

1. Масалан қаралсин: Сулейменова Г. Ж. Проблемы участия в уголовном процессе свидетелей под псевдонимом. Журнал Online.zakon.kz. 2017. –С.71-74. https:///Document/?doc_id=31424328 #pos=6; -116 .
2. Уголовно-процессуальный кодекс Российской Федерации. Статьи167, 280. от 18 декабря 2001 г. N 174-ФЗ.
3. Рекомендуемые виды практики в области защиты свидетелей при производстве по уголовным делам, касающимся организованной преступности. Организация объединенных наций, Нью-Йорк, 2008 год
4. Рекомендуемые виды практики в области защиты свидетелей при производстве по уголовным делам, касающимся организованной преступности. Организация объединенных наций, Нью-Йорк, 2008 год. – С.31.
5. Қайд этилган манбанинг 32-бети.
6. Ўша манбанинг 33-бети.
7. Бюллетень Европейского Суда по правам человека. Российское издание. М., 2003. N 1. С. 34.
8. United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 213, No. 2889
9. Kostovski v. The Netherlands, Judgement of 20 November 1989, Application No. 11451/85, Series A, No. 166; Windisch v. Austria, Judgement of 27 September 1990, Application No. 12489/86, Series A, No. 186; Lъdi v. Switzerland, Judgement of 15 June 1992, Application No. 12433/86, Series A, No. 238; and Doorson v. The Netherlands, Judgement of 26 March 1996, Application No. 20524/92, Reports 1996-II).
10. Huber B. Development of the Criminal Law: Review// European Journal of Crime, Criminal Law and Criminal Justice 1993.
11. Ashworth A. The Criminal Process : An Evaluative Study. Oxford, 1994
12. Масалан қаранг: Епихин А. Ю., Мишин А. В. Допрос потерпевшего, свидетеля под псевдонимом в досудебном и судебном производствах (уголовно-процессуальные и криминалистические аспекты). Проведение. Том 29, №4, 2019. –С.480-486; Карапетьян С.А., Олефиренко С.П. Защита участников уголовного судопроизводства: использование псевдонимов в уголовно-процессуальных законодательствах зарубежных государств постсоветского периода //Международный студенческий научный вестник. №4 (часть 4), 2015. –С.642-644.
13. Burnham W. Introduction to the Law and Legal System of the United States. West Publishing, 1994. Braithwaite J., Mugford S. Conditions of Successful

Reintegration Ceremonies: Dealing with Juvenile Offenders// British Journal of Criminology. 1994. № 34.

14. Criminal Justice. An introduction to the Criminal Justice System in England and Wales. London, 1995; Braithwaite J., Mugford S. Conditions of Successful Reintegration Ceremonies: Dealing with Juvenile Offenders// British Journal of Criminology. 1994. № 34. P 78.

15. Criminal Justice. An introduction to the Criminal Justice System in England and Wales. London, 1995.

16. Суровенко И. А., Чабукиани О. А. Проблемные аспекты обеспечения безопасности свидетеля, участвующего в следственных действиях под псевдонимом/ //Научуый диалог. 2013/ Выпуск № 7 (19): Экономика. Право. Политология. –С.142-143. Фирсов С. Н., Домнина Е. В. Особенности проведения допроса свидетеля в условиях исключаяющих его визуальное наблюдение /Пробелы в российском законодательстве. Юридический журнал. 2018, №7. –С.97-99. Дмитриева А. А. Новые правила оглашения показаний судом как усиление гарантий процессуальной безопасности участников уголовного процесса // Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного университета. Серия: Право. 2016. № 2. С. 76–79.

17. Федеративная Республика Германия. Уголоано-процессуальный кодекс. –М.: Издательская фирма “Монускрипт”, 1994.

18. Волосова Н. Ю./Volosova N. U. Matters of Russian and International Law. 2018, Vol. 8, Is. 8A Реформа уголовного судопроизводства Японии–С.183-186.

19. Ботаев М. Дж. Терговга қадар текширув институтини такомиллаштириш: Юридик фанлар бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси Автореферати. -Т., Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ички ишлар вазирлиги Академияси. 2020. –Б.13.